

Assessment of 3-Diferent Haemoglobin Estimation Methods: An Observational Comparative Study

Richa Sharma¹, Manish Kumar Jha², Sunil Kumar³, Poonam Kumari⁴

¹Tutor, Department of Pathology, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India

²Tutor, Department of Pathology, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India

³Tutor, Department of Pathology, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India

⁴Associate Professor and HOD, Department of Pathology, Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India

Received: 11-06-2023 / Revised: 21-07-2023 / Accepted: 20-08-2023

Corresponding Author: Dr. Manish Kumar Jha

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Aim: The aim of the present study was to assess the different haemoglobin estimation methods.

Methods: This study was conducted on blood samples obtained in 2 ml blood in K3 EDTA vacutainer from various indoor wards and outdoor patient departments in Pathology, Darbhanga medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India for one year. 200 adult patients sent for Hb estimation from outpatient and wards of Darbhanga medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India were included in the study.

Results: Repeatability standard deviations of Sahli's method, Drabkin's method and cell counter respectively were 0.64 g/dl, 0.40 g/dl and 0.16 g/dl. When comparing Sahli's method with Drabkin's method and cell counter, we found p value of <0.0001, suggesting significant difference between two methods whereas Drabkin's method was found to be comparable with cell counter with p value of >0.05. This showed a mean difference of 0.585 and with significant p-value of <0.001. A significant difference was found in the mean values of colorimeter and 5 part (p<0.001) despite a significant correlation between these methods.

Conclusion: Sahli's method although cheap and easy, is inaccurate and has subjective bias. So it can be used for screening purpose, but not for diagnosis and follow up of anaemia, Haemoglobin measurement by Drabkin's method is very cost effective and it is as efficient as cell counter. It is especially useful in fund deprived areas and where only haemoglobin value is required. Cell counter although highly accurate and versatile, requires good equipment, quality control, laboratory setup and trained personnel. So it should be preferably used when complete blood count is required.

Keywords: Anaemia, Automated haematology analyser, Haemoglobin estimation, Drabkin's cyanmethaemoglobin method, Sahli's method.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Anaemia is a major public health problem in developing countries. One of the reliable indicators for assessing anaemia in population is the determination of haemoglobin concentration. [1] Direct cyanmethaemoglobin method [2] is the most widely used and recommended method by the International Committee for Standardization in Haematology for quantitative estimation of haemoglobin. It involves formation of a stable compound, cyanmethaemoglobin and is relatively a simple and cost-effective method. [3] This direct method involves estimation of haemoglobin in whole blood samples using spectrophotometer and hence requires laboratory facility which limits its applicability in large-scale surveys, as transportation of whole blood in vials from long distances to central laboratories for analysis may not be feasible. Thus, indirect cyanmethaemoglobin

(filter paper) method which is based on the same principle but involves spotting of blood on filter paper is often used for the estimation of haemoglobin in population since it is simple and produces reliable results. [4] Due to the minimal invasiveness of sampling and ease of packaging and transportation from long distances, indirect cyanmethaemoglobin has been recommended, especially for those situations where laboratory is located at some distance from blood collection points. [5] Dr Robert Guthrie first used dried blood spot (DBS) specimens to measure phenylalanine in newborns for the identification of inborn errors for the detection of phenylketonuria. [6,7]

Different methods utilized for Hb estimation include acid haematin, photometric cyanmethaemoglobin estimation and automated

estimation with the help of counters. [8] The standard method for measuring hemoglobin (Hb) in human blood is the well-recognized HiCN method as recommended by the World Health Organization (WHO). [9] It is based on photometric detection of cyanmethemoglobin, as an alternative to this technology, HemoCue has developed a photometric method based on the Determination of azide methemoglobin. [10] The cyanmethaemoglobin method works on the principle of conversion of hemoglobin to cyanmethemoglobin by the addition of potassium cyanide and ferricyanide whose absorbance is measured at 540 nm in a photoelectric calorimeter against a standard solution. [11] In India approximately 70% of laboratories still use direct cyanmethaemoglobin method (HiCN) for hemoglobin estimation especially in rural areas. [12] Hemocue method and Cell counter are still costly and require good equipment, quality control, laboratory setup and trained personnel for proper functioning. But in determining the treatment protocol when other RBC indices and complete blood picture are required, automated cell counter is more useful.

The aim of the present study was to assess the different haemoglobin estimation methods.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted on blood samples obtained in 2 ml blood in K3 EDTA vacutainer from various indoor wards and outdoor patient departments in Pathology Darbhanga medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India for

one year. 200 adult patients sent for Hb estimation from outpatient and wards of Darbhanga medical College and Hospital, Darbhanga, Bihar, India were included in the study.

Samples were taken randomly and their Hb was measured by Sahli's Haemoglobinometer, Cyanmethemoglobin Method & 7-part haematology analyzer.

· Hb estimation by Sahli's haemoglobinometer (acid haematin method): Blood is mixed with N/10 HCL, resulting in the conversion of Hb to acid hematin, which was brown in colour. The solution was diluted till its colour matches with the brown coloured glass of the comparator box. The concentration of Hb was read directly.

· Hb estimation by Cyanmethemoglobin Method: Blood is diluted in a solution containing potassium cyanide and alkaline potassium ferricyanide. The latter converts Hb to methaemoglobin which is converted to cyanmethemoglobin (HiCN) by potassium cyanide. The absorbance of the solution is then measured in a spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 540 nm.

If p-value obtained from t-test is >0.05 , it means that there is no significant difference between values obtained from both methods and both methods are comparable. While if p value is <0.05 , it shows that there is significant difference between results of both methods and they are not comparable.

Results

Table 1: Comparison of Sahli's method, Drabkin's method & Cell counter

	Sahli's method	Drabkin's method	Cell counter
Range of Hb values	12.6-14.2 g/dl	12.7-14 g/dl	13-13.7 g/dl
Mean	13.27 g/dl	13.40 g/dl	13.25 g/dl
Repeatability standard deviation	0.64 g/dl	0.40 g/dl	0.16 g/dl
Method prediction range	12.8-13.7 g/dl	13.05-13.6 g/dl	13.07-13.34 g/dl

Repeatability standard deviations of Sahli's method, Drabkin's method and cell counter respectively were 0.64 g/dl, 0.40 g/dl and 0.16 g/dl. When comparing Sahli's method with Drabkin's method and cell counter, we found p value of <0.0001 , suggesting significant difference between two methods whereas Drabkin's method was found to be comparable with cell counter with p value of >0.05 .

Table 2: Mean values of Hb obtained using colorimeter and 5 part

Method	Mean	SD	Mean Diff.	t-value	p-value
Colorimeter	13.414	2.755	0.585	3.654	<0.001
5 part	12.780	2.320			

This showed a mean difference of 0.585 and with significant p-value of <0.001 . A significant difference was found in the mean values of colorimeter and 5 part ($p<0.001$) despite a significant correlation between these methods.

Discussion

There are many methods available for hemoglobin (Hb) estimation. In developing countries we are

encountered with fund crunch and overcrowded hospitals, so we must design the laboratory method in a way that it should be fast, cost effective and as accurate and reliable as possible. Sahli's method, CuSo₄ method and Drabkin's method are very cost effective. Mayang et al, in their study concluded that haemoglobin Concentration should be assessed with the direct cyanmethemoglobin method, the gold standard. [13] The photometer is easy to

transport because it is small and light; it is battery operated and gives consistent results. [14] Photometric determination of haemoglobincyanide (HiCN) is recommended as the reference method. [2]

Repeatability standard deviations of Sahli's method, Drabkin's method and cell counter respectively were 0.64 g/dl, 0.40 g/dl and 0.16 g/dl. When comparing Sahli's method with Drabkin's method and cell counter, we found p value of <0.0001, suggesting significant difference between two methods whereas Drabkin's method was found to be comparable with cell counter with p value of >0.05. This showed a mean difference of 0.585 and with significant p-value of <0.001. A significant difference was found in the mean values of colorimeter and 5 part (p<0.001) despite a significant correlation between these methods. When compared to other studies, Prashant et al 2013[15] found that Sahli's method underestimated the hemoglobin by 1.12gm/dl in venous blood and p value <0.01 between Sahli's method and cyanmethemoglobin method. In a study by P Balasubramanian & A Malathi [16], 1.13g/dl of difference was found between Sahli's method and HiCN method. However a study done by Madhura Wasnik et al using 51 subjects did not find any significant difference between results obtained from Sahli's and HiCN methods (p= 0.954 i.e. >0.05). [17]

Study by Bezerra da Silva et al comparing Sahli's method with cell counter did not find any significant difference between the two methods. [18] They found mean difference of 0.2267g/dl. An interesting study done by Dr. MP Brundha and S Priyadharshini, 2019 compared Sahli's two time average and three time average methods with automated cell counter. In this study they found Sahli's three-time average method to be most comparable with autoanalyzer with mean difference of 0.9g/dl. [19]

Conclusion

Sahli's method although cheap and easy, is inaccurate and has subjective bias. So it can be used for screening purpose, but not for diagnosis and follow up of anaemia. Haemoglobin measurement by Drabkin's method is very cost effective and it is as efficient as cell counter. It is especially useful in fund deprived areas and where only haemoglobin value is required. Cell counter although highly accurate and versatile, requires good equipment, quality control, laboratory setup and trained personnel. So it should be preferably used when complete blood count is required.

References

1. Morris SS, Ruel MT, Cohen RJ, Dewey KG, de la Brière B, Hassan MN. Precision, accuracy,

and reliability of hemoglobin assessment with use of capillary blood. The American journal of clinical nutrition. 1999 Jun 1;69(6):1243-8.

2. Zwart A, Van Assendelft OW, Bull BS, England JM, Lewis SM, Zijlstra WG. Recommendations for reference method for haemoglobinometry in human blood (ICSH standard 1995) and specifications for international haemoglobinocyanide standard. Journal of clinical pathology. 1996 Apr;49(4):271.
3. Srivastava T, Negandhi H, Neogi SB, Sharma J, Saxena R. Methods for hemoglobin estimation: A review of what works. J Hematol Transfus. 2014 Nov 2;2(3):1028.
4. Pathak P, Kapoor SK, Dwivedi SN, Singh P, Kapil U. Comparison of hemoglobin estimates from filter paper cyanmethemoglobin and HemoCue methods. Indian Journal of Community Medicine. 2004 Jul 1;29(3):149.
5. DeMaeyer EM, Dallman P, Gurney JM, Hallberg L, Sood SK, Srikantia SG, World Health Organization. Preventing and controlling iron deficiency anaemia through primary health care: a guide for health administrators and programme managers. World Health Organization; 1989.
6. Guthrie R, Susi A. A simple phenylalanine method for detecting phenylketonuria in large populations of newborn infants. Pediatrics. 1963 Sep 1;32(3):338-43.
7. Mei JV, Alexander JR, Adam BW, Hannon WH. Use of filter paper for the collection and analysis of human whole blood specimens. The Journal of nutrition. 2001 May 1; 131(5): 1631S-6S.
8. Wyne HE, Munawar F. Hemoglobin levels in day scholars and boarders of Fatima Jinnah Medical College. Pakistan J M Res 1997; 36(3): 113-4.
9. Anchinmane VT, Sankhe SV. Evaluation of hemoglobin estimation with non-cyanide alkaline haematin D-575 method. International Journal of Research in Medical Sciences. 2016 Dec 19;4(10):4297-9.
10. Rosenblit J, Abreu CR, Sztlerling LN, Kutner JM, Hamerschlak N, Frutuoso P, Paiva TR, Júnior F, da Costa O. Evaluation of three methods for hemoglobin measurement in a blood donor setting. Sao Paulo Medical Journal. 1999 May;117(3):108-12.
11. BMC Clin Pathol. 2011 Apr 21; 11:5.
12. Shah VB, Shah BS, Puranik GV. Evaluation of non-cyanide methods for hemoglobin estimation. Indian J Pathol Microbiol. 2011; 54: 764-768.
13. Sari M, Pee SD, Martini E, Herman S, Bloem MW, Yip R. Estimating the prevalence of anaemia: a comparison of three methods. Bul-

- letin of the World Health Organization. 2001; 79:506-11.
14. Robinett D, Taylor H, Stephens C. Anemia Detection in Health Services: Guidelines for Program Managers. Program for Appropriate Technology in Health; 1996.
 15. Patil PJ, Thakare GV, Patil SP. Variability and accuracy of Sahli's method in estimation of haemoglobin concentration.
 16. Balasubramaniam P, Malathi A. Comparative study of hemoglobin estimated by Drabkin's and Sahli's methods. Journal of postgraduate medicine. 1992 Jan 1;38(1):8.
 17. Madhura Wasnik, Rakhi Tirpude, Nitin Wasnik and Vijay P Agrawal. "Validation of different tests for haemoglobin estimation". International journal of biomedical and advance research ISSN: 2229-3809.
 18. Bezerra da Silva, J.F.1; Oliveira, T.N.1; Souza Filhol, S.D.; Alves, A.Q.2; Comparative evaluation of haemoglobin using N/10 hydrochloric acid versus automated method. Luso-Brazilian congress of the experimental pathology. 12/11/2011.
 19. Brundha DM, Priyadarshini S. Comparison of haemoglobin estimation by Sahli's two-time average, Sahli's three-time average methods and automated analyzer methods: A different approach in clinical pathology. Int J Clin Diagnostic Pathol [Internet]. 2019 Jul 1;2(2):291-5.